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P-D-8: Comparison of the effects of general vs. spinal anesthesia during cesarean delivery on perinatal stress in newborns (ID 40)

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Different types of newborns delivery are followed by various stress responses. Although stress has early positive effects on the organism, it can be followed by numerous negative consequences. Early onset of stress reactions in newborns can lead to development of many different sensory, emotional and intellectual deficits. The direct effects of anesthesia on vitality and adaptability to outer environment of newborn at birth, which have been evaluated by clinical and laboratory parameters, are still unknown in our country and insufficiently researched. The aim was to determine whether there is significant difference in neonatal status and stress response monitored by level of basic laboratory parameters in newborns after cesarean section under general and regional anesthesia. To give recommendations based on the obtained results in optimal type of anesthesia for caesarean section. A prospective, randomized clinical trial, conducted on Clinic for Gynecology and obstetrics in Clinical centre of Vojvodina, on healthy term newborns, born by elective cesarean section. Depending on type of anesthesia, newborns were divided into two groups of 50: caesarean section in general (O) and spinal (S) anesthesia. Neonatal status and stress response in newborns were monitored by clinical and laboratory parameters. The initial values of Apgar score and skin color were statistically better in newborns born by cesarean section under spinal anesthesia ($p=0,005$). Newborns born by cesarean section under spinal anesthesia had statistically significantly lower values of blood glucose, triglycerides and leukocytes ($p<0,001$). Following depressive effects of anesthetics, newborns vitality and Apgar score spinal anesthesia has more advantages. Cesarean section under general anesthesia is followed by higher level of stress response in newborns. Newborns born by cesarean section under spinal anesthesia have higher Apgar score and better clinical parameters. The obtained results of stress response indicators are showing benefits of cesarean section under spinal anesthesia compared to general anesthesia.

Keywords: newborn; perinatal; stress; spinal; anesthesia;